

Spectrophotometric Studies of Electron Donor-Acceptor Complexes between Polynitro Compounds and Certain Aromatic Bases at 302 K

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Manuscript received 31 August 1995, revised 12 June 1996, accepted 17 January 1997

The organic molecules by virtue of the presence of different functionalities may be either electron-rich or -deficient. As a consequence, molecular interactions arising from hydrogen bonding, loose complexation and charge transfer (CT) or electron donor-acceptor (EDA) complexes are formed. These molecules in association with suitable other molecules form CT or EDA complex either directly or in a suitable solvent. The forces responsible for holding these molecules together are intermediate between valence and London forces in that they exhibit typical colouration. The strong orientational properties of the complexes play a decisive role in the packing of molecules in crystals and liquids. It finds diverse applications in organic semiconductors, non-linear optics, drug and hormone activities besides cell-mediated metabolism in living system and as catalyst in synthetic organic chemistry. There have been extensive studies in this regard¹⁻⁴.

The present communication reports the study of charge transfer complexes of polynitro compounds as π -acceptors with some aromatic bases as n -donors in chloroform.

For the formation of charge transfer complex, viz.

$$K_C^{AD} = \frac{C_{AD}}{C_A D_D} = \frac{C_{AD}}{(C_A^0 - C_{AD})(C_D^0 - C_{AD})}$$

Since $d = \epsilon_\lambda^{AD} C_{AD}$, where d is the absorbance of the complex, the rearranged Benesi-Hildebrand (B-H) equation⁵ predicts that

$$\frac{1}{d} = \frac{1}{K_C^{AD} \epsilon_\lambda^{AD} C_A^0} \left[\frac{1}{C_D^0} \right] + \frac{1}{\epsilon_\lambda^{AD} C_A^0}$$

Thus the plot of $1/d$ vs $1/C_D^0$ is linear for 1 : 1 complex.

In a similar manner, the Scott equation⁶ predicts that

$$\frac{C_A^0 C_D^0}{d} = \frac{C_A^0 C_D^0}{\epsilon_\lambda^{AD}} + \frac{1}{K_C^{AD} \epsilon_\lambda^{AD}}$$

Thus a plot of $C_A^0 C_D^0/d$ vs C_D^0 is linear for 1 : 1 complex.

The Foster-Hammick-Wardley (F-H-W) equation⁷ predicts that

$$\frac{d}{C_D^0} = -K_C^{AD} d + K_C^{AD} \epsilon_\lambda^{AD}$$

The plot of d/C_D^0 vs d should be linear if the complex is of 1 : 1 type otherwise it will be a curve. If the complex formed is AD_n type, then plot of d/C_D^{0n} vs d will be linear.

The ionisation potential was calculated using the modified empirical equation of McConnell⁸ for TNT as acceptor,

$$h\nu_{CT} = 1.2699 I_p + 1.9 \text{ (eV)}$$

Results and Discussion

The experiment results were analysed for each system using modified (B-H)⁵, (F-H-W)⁷ and Scott⁶ equations. The plots for all the systems were found to be linear. The plots indicate 1 : 1 charge transfer complex formation and particularly FHW plots excludes the formation of higher order complexes (unpublished work), while at the same time confirming the stoichiometry borne out by modified BH and Scott plots. The calculation of K_C^{AD} and ϵ_λ^{DA} were done by regression analysis of the experimental data by LS-fit using standard computer programme. The plot of E_{CT} vs literature value of the ionisation potential (I_p) of the donors for TNT as acceptor was found to be linear. The association constant and molar extinction coefficient evaluated using FHW, Scott and BH methods show reasonable agreement and deviations, if any, can be attributed due to the inherent limitations in each of the methods. The free energy change (ΔG) has been calculated by BH method and the values are shown in Table 1.

Results of the present experimental investigations carried out on the six systems in chloroform point out the formation of 1 : 1 complex and is of $n-\pi$ type as reported earlier^{1,3}. The charge transfer band (λ_{CT}) follows the trend : NMA-TNT > DPA-DNT > NMA-DNT = MTE-TNT > BAM-TNT. However, the basicity (pK_a) of NMA, MTE, BAM, and DPA are 4.85, 4.73, 9.33 and 0.99 respectively. The comparison of EDA complex of TNT with DPA, MTE, NMA, and BAM reveals that λ_{CT} increases in the same order as the

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increasing basicity of the donor⁴, the exception being BAM, where the NH₂ group being one carbon away from the benzene ring, presumably alters the donor ability. As regards the DPA-DNT and NMA-DNT, λ_{CT} increases with decreasing basicity of the donor. This may be due to the combined steric enhancement and solvent polarisability leading to coplanarity of the donor and acceptor facilitating complexation. The thermodynamic stability, as reflected in ΔG values, seems to suggest that with the exception of NMA-TNT, all others are fairly stable and favourable. Thus the spectrophotometric study enables us to investigate not only charge transfer or electron donor-acceptor complexation, but also helps to discern its nature, stoichiometry besides quantitatively evaluating various related parameters.

TABLE 1

System	Ionisation potential*		F-H-W	Scott	B-H	F-H-W	Scott	B-H	ΔG
	$(I_p)_l$	$(I_p)_c$		K_C^{DC}			ϵ_l^{AD}		
NMA-TNT	7.32	7.04	0.499	0.506	0.503	4650	4598	4620	1.725
DPA-TNT	7.25	7.43	2.75	2.925	3.77	39.864	201	198	193-5.288
BAM-TNT	7.56	7.49	3.343	3.632	3.483	560	553	557	-3.133
MTE-TNT	7.50	7.67	4.628	5.540	4.691	630	613	623	-3.381
DPA-DNT	7.25	7.24	2.119	2.088	2.156	316	318	314	-1.929
NMA-DNT	7.32	7.72	8.02	510.645	8.216	658	630	656	-5.288

* $(I_p)_l$ = Literature value; $(I_p)_c$ = calculated value (eV) of the donors.
 K_C^{AD} (dm³ mol⁻¹); ΔG (B-H) (kJ mol⁻¹); ϵ_l^{DA} ($\times 10^{-1}$ m² mol⁻¹).

The study reveals that the stoichiometry of the CT complex in the aforesaid systems is 1 : 1 and of $n-\pi$ type. The CT band increases with donor basicity, exception being NMA-TNT system. The association constant, molar extinction coefficient, ionisation potential and free energy change can be determined to a fair degree of accuracy without having resort to complicated equations. The ionisation potential of the donor calculated empirically agrees more closely with the literature value.

Experimental

The electron acceptors 2,4-dinitrotoluene and 2,4,6-trinitrotoluene were synthesised as reported in the literature⁹ and their purity was checked by m.p., ir and nmr spectra. *N*-Methylamine (NMA) (Merck), diphenylamine (DPA) (Ranbaxy), benzylamine (BAM), (SD's Fine Chemicals) and *m*-toluidine (MTE) (Fluka) were used. Chloroform was purified as described in the literature¹⁰. The electronic spectra (CHCl₃) were recorded on a Shimadzu UV 160 spectrophotometer. The values of λ_{max} of DNT and TNT are 248.6 and

250 nm, and that for NMA, DPA, BAM and MTE are 255.2, 286.6, 260 and 248 nm respectively. The λ_{CT} values for the systems NMA-TNT, NMA-DNT, DPA-DNT, BAM-TNT and MTE-TNT were found to be 426, 368, 381, 357 and 368 nm respectively. It is obvious that the λ_{CT} is well-resolved and distinct from the λ_{max} of the pure compounds.

Stock solutions of the donor and acceptor were prepared, such that the donor concentration was very much higher than that of the acceptor, and from that a series of solution mixtures of the donor and acceptor were prepared while holding the acceptor concentration constant for each system but varying the donor concentration. The absorbance (d) for each solution was measured. From the knowledge of the λ_{CT} , the charge transfer energy was computed.

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